

READING HABITS AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS**Mrs. Kadambari H Manjrekar***Librarian, VPM's B.N.Bandodkar College of Science, Thane, Maharashtra***Ms Divya Nair,***Asst Professor, VPM's B.N.Bandodkar***Abstract:**

Reading helps to gain the knowledge, build analytical thinking and improve the capabilities of an individual. The present study is an attempt to know the reading habits of Undergraduate students (of B.N. Bandodkar College of Science, Thane, and Autonomous). The survey method found the most useful to collect maximum responses. It was observed that 91% students like the general reading but 9% don't like the general reading. In this 21st century where electronic medium is most popular, but it is found in this study that students preferred both the medium print and electronic for reading. From this survey few voracious readers were also found who are reading more than 12 hours per week apart from their regular studies.

Keywords: *Reading habit, print media, inspirational books, teacher's guidance*

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Introduction:

Reading is an important habit of an individual. Reading makes an individual wiser. Reading helps to gain the knowledge, build analytical thinking and improve the capabilities of an individual. Now reading habits in young generation is shrinking because of many other avenues like television, mobile, internet etc. It is duty of the parents to develop the reading habits among their children right from their childhood.

Majid and Tan (2007) mentioned that it is widely acknowledged that the lifelong habit of reading can best be inculcated and nurtured at an early age. It is a general observation that there is an over emphasis on study related reading thus ignoring the recreational or free voluntary reading among students. Shafi described, “ reading is the ability to recognise and

examine words or sentences and understand the information within. It is a cognitive process of understanding a written linguistic message and to examine and grasp the meaning of written or printed characters, words or sentences”.

Review of Literature:

Shafi and Loan (2010) identified reading is a basic skill for lifelong learning and lifelong reading can be established through leisure reading. They further observed that the students also show interest in other subjects, so it is duty of the Document/Book Selection Committee to build a balanced collection of quality material in libraries to satisfy the reading needs of all. The study pointed that females proved to be more dominant than males in reading culture. **Adnan, Akram and Akram (2016)** mentioned that reading assists the friendly and focussed function in day to day life. They have also explained in their study about Robinson SQ3R five steps to enhance reading habits – Survey, question, read, recite and review. To develop reading habits among the individuals, parents and teachers serve an important role. **Fatiloro et al (2017)** conducted a survey of reading habit among Colleges of Education students in Oyo in which they found there is the need for students to read more of novels and articles in order to boost their vocabulary. **Kay (2005)** in his survey of Reading habits of Undergraduate business students showed that 84 percent of the students read college textbooks and 61 percent read business related publications on the internet at least once a week. However, 16 percent read textbooks and 39 percent read business related publications monthly or less. **Majid and Tan (2007)** in their study conducted a survey of 440 upper primary students reading habits and preferences of children behind reading, resulted that students were motivated to read for academically related reasons such as to improve language skills because stressful Singapore education system which places high emphasis on meritocracy and good grades.. Reading is at third place of choice after hobbies and internet. They also pointed out that girls are more avid than boys. **Satriani (2019)** found that online reading resources also provided positive changes for the learners who have low motivation in reading to be a fun reading activity. Having support from teacher, parents, and environment help the learners establish their reading habit. The significant reason of learners in getting the reading habit was to complete the task. The result implies that the learners expected to read more intensively to get better reading habit. **Naveed (2018)** studied the holistic view on trends of reading paperback books and did not aim to confer

any particular aspect or impact of reading books on respondents. However, the findings have shown that paperback books still are of great importance and significant driving force when it comes to reading for pleasure and/or academic purposes among university students. **Nor and Karim (2007)** revealed that the web site is seen as an increasingly important reading source. Significant differences exist between academic programs and types of reading materials and reading resources particularly use the web sites. Some differences in reading habits and attitudes were also observed between male and female participants.

Statement of Problem

In the 21st century, there are various options available to the young generation for passing the time. During earlier time, Reading was leisure for young generation, but now we have to behind the students for the reading purpose.

To become perfect person, one must need to read. For young generation to get varied experience, they must read apart from their curricular reading. Thus, it is a need to study the reading habits of college going students. This reading habit will be their weapon for getting and continuation of their career.

Objectives:

- i. To study reading habits among UG students.
- ii. To find out time spent on general reading apart from their curricular reading.
- iii. To identify type of material read by the students.
- iv. To study factors helped in developing the reading habit and impact of reading.
- v. To analyse gender wise difference in type of material read.

Scope:

The present study involved an extensive survey about reading habits of First year, Second year and Third year undergraduate students of VPM's B.N. Bandodkar College of Science, Thane (BNB).

Methodology

The survey was conducted during April 2020 to May 2020. The well-structured questionnaire was developed to collect the response. The questionnaire was sent to the total 1836 admitted students. The questionnaire developed with the help of Google form in which various sections were created as personal information, gender, liking of reading, factors influencing, type of

material to read etc. All questions were Multiple Choice Questions. Total 407 responses received, which was validated and then data analysis task started. The results found are presented in graphs and tables form.

Table 1 : Classwise bifurcation of responses received

	Response received	Female	Male
FYBSc	192	119	73
SYBSc	130	77	53
TYBSc	85	56	29
Total	407	252	155

Discussion and Findings:

- A. Liking of Reading:** It is very much essential that one must have the habit of reading. To know the students liking about reading, it is found from the data that 9.07% students don't like reading whereas 90.93% students responded they like the reading.
- B. Time spent on reading other than studies:** Being a science faculty students, for them maximum time is spend for academic assessments. In general it is observed that the students spend 5-7 hours per day for academic work of attending lectures and practical. Apart from academic reading, it is inevitable for them to read other material than the curriculum. It is found that 19.16% students read 1-3 hours per week, 14.50 % students read 3-5 hours per week, 5.66% students read 5-8 hours per week, 19.41% read 8-12 hours per week, 4.91% students read more than 12 hours per week and 36.36 % read less than 1 hour per week. Thus the result shows that, though students are busy with academic activities, still they spent significant time for general reading apart from academics. It is observed from the study that time spent on reading is not dependent on class

Table 2 : Time spent on reading other than studies

CLASS	Less than 1 hour	1-3 hours	3-5 hours	5-8 Hours	8-12 hours	More Than 12 hours	Grand Total
F.Y.B.Sc	64	43	27	14	34	10	192
S.Y.B.Sc	53	22	18	6	24	7	130
T.Y.B.Sc	31	13	14	3	21	3	85
Grand Total	148	78	59	23	79	20	407

C. Format of material for reading purpose : In this 21st century students have the options to read the material in print and electronic media. Print material is traditional form of reading. The study resulted that 22.85% students prefer print format, 9.1% students preferred e-format whereas 68% students preferred both the formats.

Table 3 : Format of material for reading purpose

Row Labels	Print	Electronic	Both	Grand Total
F.Y.B.Sc	46	17	129	192
S.Y.B.Sc	30	14	85	129
T.Y.B.Sc	17	6	63	86
Grand Total	93	37	277	407

D. Type of material read by students: Gender wise: Any type of reading helps to gain the knowledge. Above table describes about diverse types of reading material like newspapers, magazines, journals, novels, e-books, online articles and blogs. The most common types of reading material is newspaper responded by 54.54% students. This is followed by Novels (38.08%), online articles (36.85%), e-books (28%), magazines 24.07%, blogs 19.66% and journals 18.43%. The classification of data on the basis of gender reveals that the male students mainly read newspapers, online articles, e-books, novels followed by journals, blogs and magazines. Findings further disclosed that newspaper is common material used by male and female students. Female students read more novels than male students.

Diverse type of reading helps the individual to develop the personality. Present study is conducted on the population of science faculty background. Table 4 indicate significant observation that, the efforts must be taken to increase the habit of using journals among this population, for better scientific writing. Even very few female students read the journals as compared to male students.

Table 4 : Type of material read by students

Sr No	Type of Material	Female	Male	Total	%
1	Newspapers	133	89	222	54.54
2	Novels	112	43	155	38.08
3	Online articles	84	66	150	36.85
4	E-books	69	45	114	28
5	Magazines	64	32	96	24.07
6	Blogs	45	35	80	19.66
7	Journals	37	38	75	18.43

E. Types of books read: The habit of reading started from the childhood. Initially story books are preferred to read. As an individual grow, this habit of reading goes on changing to different type of material. From this survey the facts come out that majority of the students preferred to read historical books and 58.9% students reported this material reading most of the times. Further Comedy books, scientific books, Inspirational books, novels and biographies are also popular among the students. Spiritual, books related to sports, mythological and philosophical books were not preferred by the students. Students gave least response (15.72%) for books related to economic books.

Table 5 :

Sr No	Type of books	No. of Responses	%
1	Historical	238	58.47
2	Scientific	198	48.65
3	Comedy	193	47.42
4	Inspirational	193	47.42
5	Novels	163	40.05
6	Suspence	159	39.07
7	Biography	146	35.87
8	Autobiographies	117	28.75
9	Spiritual	115	28.25
10	Mythological	113	27.76
11	Philosophical	106	26.04
12	Sports	96	23.59
13	Geographical	83	20.39
14	Political	79	19.41
15	Economic	64	15.72

F. Factors helped in developing reading habits: Many times it happen that there may be any factor that influences an individual to do any task. **Adnan, Akram and Akram (2016)** pointed out that to develop reading habits among the individuals, parents and teachers play an important role. A teacher can influence students' attitudes, purposes, literacy choices and their commitment to live. Thus to find what factors make the students to develop reading habit, it is found that own hobby is the major factor to develop reading habit, which is a positive sign that students would like to read. It shows that they themselves having the feeling of reading. Further factors to develop their reading habits are parental guidance, motivation from teachers, need of time and friends.

Graph 1 :

G. Impact of reading: It is evident that reading habit helped the respondents to enhance the vocabulary. Majority of the participants expressed 44.96% that reading helps them to increase their vocabulary, which is followed by getting new ideas by 43% respondents. Positive thinking always helps. Thus 34.40% respondents replied that reading habit brings positive transformation in them. Quite a few 20.39% respondents find solution for their problems after reading. Study reveals that majority of students got benefitted to enhance their vocabulary and gives new ideas. Which is followed by positive transformation in them, boosting confidence, develop the personality, and found solution to their problem.

Table 6 : Impact of reading

Sr No	Details	FYBSc	SYBSc	TYBSc	Total	%
1	Boost Confidence	53	46	32	131	32.18
2	Gives new ideas	79	60	40	179	43.98
3	Gives me new direction	48	36	25	109	26.78
4	Positive transformation in me	64	45	31	140	34.40
5	Helps to develop my personality	66	36	32	134	32.92
6	Offer solution to my problems	36	22	25	83	20.39
7	Just add information	61	39	30	130	31.94
8	Enhance Vocabulary	83	58	42	183	44.96
9	All of the above	79	49	38	166	40.79

Conclusion:

This study throw the light on reading habit of UG students of Science faculty students. This study reveals that being science faculty students, apart from their busy schedule they spent significant time for general reading excluding of academic reading. The study confirms that reading is a hobby in many respondents. In today's world of e-media, students don't required only electronic reading, but they preferred print and electronic both medium for reading.

For overall growth of the students it is essential that they must do reading on varied topics and through this study it come out that 58.47% students read historical books, 48.65% read scientific books, 47.42 % read inspirational and comedy books. Study reveals that majority of students got benefitted by nurturing reading habit to enhance their vocabulary and gives new ideas. Study reveals that the newspaper is common material used by male and female students and Female students read more novels than male students.

This study can be considered as case study of science faculty college, which will be helpful further for conducting research of larger population and mix groups of faculties. This study is limited to one college and few variables related to reading habits were studied. The other variables can be studied further like difficulties in reading, any inspirations come out in form experience etc.

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